

Maysilo Malabon Water Bacteriological Analysis: Plastic Decomposing Bacteria Phase 1

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Abstract:- Plastic-decomposing bacteria were isolated from the muddy estuary shoreline of Maysilo Malabon. Isolates that grew on MacConkey agar were included in the study, eliminating any gram-positive. The surface texture of the high-density polyethylene plastic (HDPE) strips immersed in the isolate suspensions as well as the change in tensile strength were used to gauge plastic material decomposition. The isolates were found to be highly similar to *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and to *Enterobacter*, *Paenibacillus*, and *Pseudomonas* when subjected to 16S RNA sequencing. Catalase and oxidase tests were used to confirm the identity of the isolates.

Keywords:- *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Enterobacter*, *Paenibacillus*, *Pseudomonas* High-Density Polyethylene Plastic

I. INTRODUCTION

The water quality in domestic areas close to the river bank of Maysilo Malabon stands as a prime item for investigation, apart from the efforts to improve the system of pipes fittings, appurtenances from drainage outlets of residential areas to the river systems are currently being done. In 2019, the government of Malabon welcomed a bid from a company for the improvement of the sewage treatment plant of its local hospital.

However, it is of much interest to environmental scientists and environmental managers how the estuary coastline and waters of Maysilo Malabon can be restored to a natural resource of life. The interest to make it useful while it teems with all kinds of solid wastes- paper, metals, plastics, and bottles remains. The dying river has resigned to a condition when the only metabolic activity dominating the area is just the microbes that eat and decompose the trash. From this, the idea that useful microorganisms can be recovered, cultured, and used for enhancing bioremediation has surfaced.

First identified in 2016 by scientists from Kyoto Institute of Technology and Keio University who studied a community of microorganisms from sediments contaminated by polyethylene plastics in Sakai, Japan, *Ideonella sakaiensis*, thriving in muddy areas wrought by plastic that congest waterways may also be found on the banks of the Maysilo Malabon river.

Gram-negative, aerobic rod-shaped bacteria, the colony-forming units of *I. sakaiensis* are circular, smooth,

and colorless. A cell is 0.6-0.8 um in width and 1.2 -1.5 um long, are equipped with one flagellum (Yoshida et al. (2016). *I. sakaiensis* also oxidase and catalase-positive surviving at a pH range of 5.5 to 9.0 (optimally at 7 to 7.5) and a temperature of 15–42°C (optimally at 30–37°C). Raut (2015) studied microbial degradation of high-density polyethylene. Isolation of plastic digesting enzymes is a potential bio-remediation procedure to eliminate faster plastic waste materials that clog and pollute the environment.

This study aimed to isolate, characterize and identify bacterial isolates from the muddy shoreline waters of the Maysilo Malabon estuary, that can affect the degradation of high-density polyethylene plastics.

II. METHODS

Collection of the samples of the river water from Maysilo Malbon, followed by serial dilution, culturing on nutrient agar, then on MacConkey agar to eliminate the Gram positive bacteria, the search for bacterial isolates that can degrade high-density polyethylene plastic was conducted. Ocular characterization of the colony growths was done.

A catalase test using hydrogen peroxide droplets was done on smears of the bacterial slant cultures.

➤ Plastic Strip Degradation Test

Cultured unknown bacterial isolate suspensions in test tubes were made to contain a small strip of HDPE plastic each, then incubated at 30-35 degrees for weeks and at the longest for 36 days. Special setups to check on temperature variation during incubation were done also.

To check for evidence of plastic degradation, the plastic strips were washed with distilled water and then examined of surface texture under the light microscope.

To identify the isolates, the unknown bacterial cultures were sent for Sanger sequencing to the Philippine Genome Center, University of the Philippines, Diliman Quezon City, Philippines.

➤ Simple Tensile Strength Test

The strength of the plastic strips was tested using a spring balance hook to pull the strip to the elastic limit that is until it snaps off.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The water samples collected from the Maysilo Malabon estuary were subjected to serial dilution. Inoculation by pour plating the samples of different dilutions (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}), on nutrient agar, followed by incubation at 35 degrees Celsius was done. Randomly individual colony-forming units were isolated using an inoculating needle and then sub-cultured on nutrient agar. All those that turned out to be Gram negative, turning pink to red on MacConkey agar, thereafter were after sub-cultured on nutrient agar slants (Please see Appendix A).

➤ *Colony Growth Characterization:*

Fig 1 Images of colony growths on three of the agar slants prepared form different dilution factors and at different depths. Left: water sample A (10^{-2}) from the depths of 2.5 M; middle (10^{-3}) from the same depth; and right- from water sample (10^{-1}) collected from a depth of 6 meters.

Most of the unknown bacterial isolates as shown in Figure 1 and in Appendix A. are off - white colonies with irregular edges. Particularly sample G, third from right, has undulating margins.

➤ *Colony Forming Unit Characterization*

Table 1 Colony Forming Units Characteristics on Agar slants

Bacterial Isolate Code / ID	Serial dilution Factor	Depth in meters (m).	Colony Forming Unit (CFU) Characteristics
A <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	10-2	2.5	Non-lactose fermenting; brown in MacConkey agar; very granular, somewhat undulating colonies on Nutrient agar (NA)
B, D1, E, H, I suspected as <i>A. baumannii</i>	10-3	2.5	Non-lactose fermenting, brown in MacConkey Agar; granular CFU on NA; D1 with irregular hairy-like edges digging deep to the bottom of the slant; somewhat dry granular colonies; spots of brown CFU near the bottom of the slant; turns to very dark brown colonies
<i>C-Paenibacillus sp.</i> and isolate J (for confirmation)	10-2	4	Opaque, somewhat dry colonies; but J is a transparent colony on NA slant, non-lactose fermenting, digging close to the bottom of the MacConkey agar slant
4,7, K,12, 6 suspected to be <i>Enterobacter</i> ; Isolate G - suspected as <i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	10-1	6	Slow growing on NA; red on MacConkey agar; colonies seem to prefer to be near the bottom of the slants where the condition is anaerobic; K isolate developed sepia brown colonies after 5 months; Isolate 12 has an undulating lawn of CFU's;
Unknown - N, 5, 1, 2, 11	10-2	6	Slimy, browning white, mucous CFUs; N isolate, catalase + turned into sepia-colored colonies after 5 months; Isolate 11 is light pink on MacConkey agar slant
Unknown isolate 14			Isolate 14 is an opaque lawn of CFU's n NA slant and non-lactose fermenting on Mac Conkey
Unknown isolate	10-1	Mud	Brown CFU's reaching down to the bottom of the MacConkey

from the mud			agar slant
Unknown - 9, 10	10-1	2.5	Moving deep clear to the bottom of the slant where the condition is partially anaerobic. Isolate 10 is with deeply undulating edges, and almost transparent CFU's on NA slant
Unknown -P	10--2	10	Mucous off-white CFU's on NA slant
Isolate F reported as <i>Acinetobacter</i>	10-2	4	Mucous granular appearance
Isolate I- suspected as <i>A. baumannii</i>	10-3	2.5	White tiny granular colonies
Unknown Isolate 4	10-1	6	Off-white with irregular edges; Non-lactose fermenting on MacConkey agar

Acinetobacter baumannii are Gram -negative somewhat round bacilli that are catalase positive and oxidase negative. They are also non-lactose fermenting lactobacillus but look like mucous round colonies that project a granular appearance on nutrient agar.

The genus *Enterobacter* includes facultative anaerobic Gram-negative bacilli that ferment lactose and glucose, having catalase, that are found in sewage, wastewater and soil. These features are seen in unknown isolates 4,7, K 12, and 6. NCBI PBLAST of Sanger sequence results report isolate G, later found to be oxidase positive, as *Enterobacter*, a genus inclusive of catalase positive and oxidase negative rods.

Pseudomonas is another genus reported for isolate G which like the former has both the catalase and oxidase enzymes.

➤ *Catalase Test and Oxidase Test Results (Appendix E and F).*

Most of the unknown isolates that were collected from the muddy water depths of six meters were found to be catalase positive. One unknown isolate from the mud (Unknown isolate 3) was also found to be catalase positive; another turned out to be negative.

The Sanger sequence outcomes for bacterial isolates with codes A, B, C and D1 were given high percentages of identical matches with *Acinetobacter* (93.71%) for isolates A, B and D1 , and *Paenibacillus* (91.49%) for isolate C (Philippine Genome Center , Diliman, Quezon City).

Table 2 gives the literature data on the responses of *Acinetobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas* and *Paenibacillus* to catalase using 3% hydrogen peroxide and oxidase tests using discs of tetramethyl phenylene diamine (TMPD) which served as sources of electrons to the bacterial cells.

Table 2 Oxidase and Catalase Test Responses of known Bacterial groups

Bacterial Group	Catalase test response	Oxidase test Response
<i>Acinetobacter sp.</i>	Positive +	Negative -
<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>	Positive +	Negative -
<i>Paenibacillus</i>	Negative -	Positive +
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	Positive +	Positive +

Table 3 below gives the actual results of catalase and oxidase tests given to the unknown bacterial isolates. Isolate A which has a Sanger sequence similarity of 93% to *Acinetobacter baumannii*; similarly, isolate 1 is catalase positive and oxidase. Isolate G has catalase-oxidase responses similar to *Pseudomonas* to which it was reported to have 90.10% similarity at E=0.006, with 70% query cover and 45% maximum score; it showed positive for both catalase and oxidase enzymes.

Isolate - G that has 93.10 % similarity (E= 0.006), at a greater probability (E = 90 e7) with 90% similarity to *Enterobacter* which is catalase positive, but oxidase negative, was also given in its NCBI nucleotide BLAST results.

None paralleled the catalase - oxidase responses of *Enterobacter sp.* (catalase positive and oxidase negative) and that of *Paenibacillus* which is catalase negative and oxidase positive.

Majority of the unknown isolates coded as P; 10; 7; D and E share the same responses with *Ideonella sakaiensis*, an established plastic decomposing bacteria, that is both catalase and oxidase positive (Oshida et al., 2016).

Isolate F had 94% similarity to *Acinetobacter* and *Klebsiella* in the NCBI BLAST results, but unlike the catalase positive and oxidase negative responses of these two genera, isolate F showed positive for both enzymes (Appendix E and F).

Table 3 Oxidase Test and Catalase Test Reactions of the unknown Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial Isolate Code /ID	Catalase test response	Oxidase test Response (+/-)	Bacterial Isolate Code /ID	Catalase test response	Oxidase test Response (+/-)
4	+	-	2	+	-
Unknown C	+	-	A (<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>)	-	+
P	+	+	D	+	+
10	+	+	E	+	+
G (<i>Pseudomonas</i>)	+	+	7	+	+
O	+	+	12	+	+
F(<i>Acinetobacter</i> ?)	+	+	14	+	-
D	+	+	B	-	-
1	+	-			

➤ *Bacterial Potency*

Table 4 Potency of the bacterial isolates to grow even in the absence nutrients- neither plastic nor culture medium, that is when grown only in plain sterile distilled water

Bacterial Isolates Code with or without plastic strip immersed	Number of days in the suspension	Turbidity based on McFarland Standard	Potency (potent ; + ; No potency detected (-)) and other Features	Catalase test response (+/-)	Water Depth where sample water collection site in meters	dilution factor
Unknown -1(without plastic)	50	Approximately equal to 0.5 McFarland (1Billion cells)	No potency detected	+	2.5 m	10-2
Unknown -J without plastic	110	Approximately equal to 1Mc Farland (2 Billion cells)	++	+	4 m	10-2
Unknown-3 without plastic	50	clear	Not potent	- /+	mud	
Unkown-11 without plastic	50		Not potent	+	6	10-2
Unknown-Jc without plastic	150	a slight change in turbidity	Not potent (-)	+	4	10-2
<i>Pseudomonas</i> -G with plastic	64	approximately equal to 0.5 McFarland	No detectable potency	+	6 m	10-1
Unknown- N; 2; 5 (w/o plastic)	99	Approximately equal to 0.5 Mc Farland, 1 Billion cells	Potent (+)	+	6 m	10-2
Unknown -P (without plastic)	43	approximately 0.5 McFarland turbidity level	No potency detected	+(slow reaction)	10m ?	10-2
Unknown 14	50	approximately 0.5 McFarland turbidity level	Potent (+) lactose fermenting	+	6 m	10-1
Unknown 5; I; 11; 2, N (all without plastic)	More than 3 months	<< 0.5	Not Potent (-)	+	6 m	10-2
Unknown 2; I	50	< 0.5	Not Potent(-)	+	6	10-2
Unknown 12, G, 4, K, 12, 14, 6 without	50	clear or with no turbidity	Not Potent (-)	+	6	10-1

plastic						
Unknown 4 - without plastic	50	no turbidity change	Not Potent)	+	6m	10-1
Unknown 9 (without plastic)	50	slightly turbid	Not Potent	+	2.5	10-1
Unknown - I without plastic	47	no turbidity	Not potent	+	2.5 m	10-3
Unknown - F without plastic	47	<0.5	Not Potent	+	6 m	10-1
Unknown - 6	47	no change in turbidity	Not Potent / catalase +	+	6 m	-
Unknown -K with plastic	47	approximately 0.5	No Potency detected (-)	+	6 m	10-1
A. baumannii -D1 with plastic strip immersed	150	nearly 1.0 McFarland	Potent (+)	+	2.5 m	10-3
Paenibacillus C - without plastic	177	> 1.0 McFarland	Potent (+)	+	4 m	10-2
Unknown - I	43	no change in turbidity	No potency detected	+	2.5	10-3
Unknown 7, K, 12, 6, all without plastic	64	> 0.5	No potency detected	+	6	10-1
Unknown-without plastic	47	no difference in turbidity	No potency detected	+		10-1
Unknown - K with plastic	47	no difference in turbidity	No potency detected	+	6	10.00-1

The bacterial isolates from the Maysilo Malabon muddy estuary were held in suspensions for several months. These isolates were only inoculated in plain sterile distilled water; some with HDPE strips added; some were not. Table 2 shows that the bacterial isolates in nutrient -lacking medium like plain distilled water would take more than three months- 99 to 150 or 180 days before they, like *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Paenibacillus sp.*, could show a detectable change in turbidity exceeding 0.5 (1.5×10^8 colony forming units, which is the initial turbidity level. The increase in the suspension turbidity approximates 1.0 McFarland. The 177-day-old isolate C, reported as *Paenibacillus* and inoculated in plain distilled water without plastic, demonstrated high turbidity; *A. baumannii*, isolate D was immersed with a plastic strip which it could have used to demonstrate turbidity greater than 1.5×10^8 cells (0.5 McFarland). Younger cultures a little over two (2) months cannot demonstrate detectable potency which means that

they went through low growth and survival rates in a nutrient-depleted medium, even in cases when the supplementary diet which is a strip of HDPE plastic was added; this is shown by isolate K, suspected to be *Enterobacter*. Regardless of the dilution factor, or the depth at which the water samples were collected, these held through.

➤ Observations on Plastic Degrading Ability of the Bacterial Isolates

A 2x 4.3 mm square of plastic (High-density polyethylene) strip was immersed in each of the plain sterilized distilled water in test tubes. Using an inoculating loop each of these 15ml regular test tubes with a plastic strip was inoculated with a scoopful of bacteria to make a 5ml 0.5 McFarland (approximately one billion bacterial cells) turbid suspension. Figure 2 and Appendix B show the results.

Fig 2 Turbidity is seen to be remarkable in the test tubes with plastic strips. The control test tubes which are without plastic strips are clearer as marked by the clear zone on top of the water layer. Isolate D is *Paenibacillus sp.*; G is *Enterococcus sp.*

The turbidity that developed in the test tubes with plastic strips demonstrates that the bacterial isolates multiply even on plain distilled water, presumably deriving nutrients from the plastic strip immersed in the tube.

➤ *Surface Erosion of the Plastic strips*

Fig 3 The Image of the Plastic Strip from the Control 14-Day Old Suspension with Plain Distilled Water Only

Fig 4 Image (100x) of the plastic strip after immersion in around 0.5-1.0 McFarland bacterial isolate suspension (B, dilution factor 10^{-2} sourced at river water depth of 4 meters) for fourteen days, incubated at 30- 35 degrees Celsius

The change in the texture of the plastic strip is obvious as shown by its slimy appearance after having been immersed for 14 days in a bacterial isolate suspension, (0.5 to 1.0 McFarland) approximately having 1.5×10^8 to 3×10^8 colony-forming units.

- *The Time Period of Exposure to Bacterial Isolate Suspension*

Fig 5 Plastic Strip Images Under the 40x HPO after one Month of Immersion in *Acinetobacter Baumannii* Suspension.

Compared to the plastic strip in Figure 4 which is a strip exposed to bacterial suspension after 14 days this plastic strip whose surface is shown in Figure 5 after having been immersed for a month in the bacterial isolate (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) suspension, is visibly more eroded with patches of damaged areas. Sanger sequencing results show that both isolates A and B are identified as *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

It is noted that the degradation of the HDPE strip by these bacterial isolates is a function of time. At

temperatures between 30-35 degrees C, the plastic decomposing activity seems to be enhanced.

- *Exposure to Temperature Variation*

This plastic strip that was immersed in a bacterial suspension (*A. baumannii*) for two months at varying temperatures from 45 degrees for one week, followed by a longer exposure to temperatures between 30-35 degree Celsius shows swelling up of fibers and virtual loss of texture integrity.

Fig 6 Image (100x) of the HDPE plastic strip after 2- month immersion in the bacterial isolate B 10-2 4M 2/12 TR, earlier subjected to 45 degrees Celsius for around one week, then incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius for the next weeks until the photo is taken. Sanger sequence results identified isolate B as *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

The change in the texture of the High-Density polyethylene (HDPE) plastic strips into a roughened swollen texture after immersion in bacterial isolate suspensions indicate an indication of decomposition (Figures 7, 8, and 9).

Fig 7 The High-Density Polyethylene Plastic Strip Surface Erosion after Immersion in *Acinetobacter Baumannii* Isolate Suspension for Three Months and Five Days.

Fig 8 The High Density Polyethylene Surface Erosion by *Enterobacter* in the Isolate Suspension for Three Months and Five Days.

Fig 9 The High Density Polyethylene Plastic Surface Erosion by *Paenibacillus Sp.* the Bacterial Isolate in Suspensions C and J for Three Months and Five Days.

The unknown bacterial isolates were identified using Sanger sequencing at the Philippine Genome Center in the University of the Philippines Diliman Quezon City as *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Paenibacillus sp.* and *Enterobacter sp.* If not *Pseudomonas sp.*

Figures 7 and 8 demonstrate the radical distortion of the plastic strip surface texture after exposure to these two species respectively, for three months and 6 days.

Grady et al. (2016) reviewed the various industrially important enzymes in *Paenibacillus*, an opportunistic human pathogen but of great utility in agriculture, pharmacy and medicine.

Elahi et al. (2021) includes *Paenibacillus* and *Bacillus* species among the microbes with the ability to decompose plastics.

Acinetobacter baumannii which are Gram negative cocci were reported by Takoi et al. (2019) to have been easily transmitted from gloves to environmental surfaces; such were easily transferred from nitrile gloves to polypropylene plastic, and compared to other gram-negative bacteria, can become agents of nosocomial

infections, supporting the finding that *Acinetobacter baumannii* is a high density plastic decomposing bacteria.

The HDPE plastic strips were detected to have changes in tensile strength after immersion in the bacterial isolate suspensions (Table 5).

Table 5 Strength Test Results of the Plastic Strips after Exposure to Bacterial in Suspensions for 76 Days.

Code /Identification	Force in Newtons (N)required to break the HDPE plastic strip	Code/ Identification	Force required to break the HDPE Plastic strip	Code/ Identification	Force required to break the HDPE plastic strip
Control (plastic strips in distilled water)	5; 8; 7.2; 6.8; 7.3; 7.3; 5.4; 7; 7; 8 Average: 6.9	4	6.2	11	3.8
O (unknown)	4	7	12.5	10 (unknown)	3
J	8 to 10	9 (unknown)	6.8	6	7
7	12	8 (unknown)	4.2	5	11.5
12	5	1	3	P	11.8
3 (unknown sourced from the mud)	8.5	2 (unknown)	5	14	6.5; 3

Table 3 shows the results of immersing the HDPE plastic strips, each in an unknown bacterial isolate suspension incubated at 35 degrees Celsius.

The average strength of the high density polyethylene plastic (HDPE) strips that measured 10mm x 50mm, used for comparison in were simply immersed in distilled water but subjected to the same incubation temperature, was found to be 6.9 Newtons(N).

The HDPE strips with Isolates 7, and 6, suspected to be *Enterobacter sp.* snapped off when pulled over the spring balance at 7-12 N- showing that the bacterial isolates have not effected reduction in the HDPE strip strength. However, the plastic strip immersed with unknown Isolate 14 broke apart at 6.5 to 3 N- a reduction in strength by 5- 50%. The HDPE strip with unknown isolate 1 required 3 N to snapped off. The unidentified isolates 10 and 11 resulted in only 3 N and 3.8 N respectively to break off the high density plastic strip, a reduction in the HDPE plastic strength by 50- 37%.

IV. CONCLUSION

The water samples collected from the muddy waters of the Maysilo Malabon estuary were found to harbor plastic decomposing bacteria, namely *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Enterobacter sp.*, *Pseudomonas sp.*, and *Paenibacillus sp.*

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APPENDIX A

➤ Images of Nutrient agar subcultures of Gram – negative bacterial isolates; all were colony forming units isolated for MacConkey agar slants.

APPENDIX B

➤ Close up of images of the control bacterial suspension without plastic added , and the test tube suspension with plastic strip added.

• Comparison of the Bacterial Suspension Turbidity Levels in the Test Tubes with and Without the Plastic Strips.

APPENDIX C

➤ Surface Erosion of the High Density Polyethylene Plastic

High Density OLYETHYLENE PLASTIC (HDPE) DECOMPOSING ACTIVITY OF MAYSISLO MALABON RIVER WATER BACTERIAL ISOLATES

Comparative ocular features of the HDPE plastic strips after incubation with bacterial isolates. Note that the **Control** (without bacterial isolate) has a rough texture. The plastic strips immersed in bacterial isolate suspensions (0.5- 1.0 McFarland have developed slimy – looking less translucent but swelled up surfaces; observed last February 10, 2023).

Control 14- day old HDPE plastic strip incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius, immersed in pure distilled water only.

A 10-2 2.4 M 23/11 1/12: PET strip after two months and ten days immersion in around 1.0 McFarland bacterial isolate suspension, then incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius for the next weeks until the photo istaken.

The plastic strip after immersion in approximately 1.0 McFarland suspension(10-2 2.4 M 23/11 1/12- *A. baumannii*), incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius, for one month until the photo was taken.

The plastic strip that was first immersed in approximately 0.5-1.0 McFarland bacterial isolate(B 10-2 4M 2/12 TR- *A. baumannii*) suspension to room temperature (25 degrees Celsius) for one week, then incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius for the next 7 weeks, i.e., almost two months until the photo was taken.

Plastic strip immersed in isolate B 10-2 4M 2/12 TR for two months;it was earlier subjected to 6 degrees Celsius for around one week, then incubated at 30-35 degrees Celsius.

APPENDIX C

➤ *Bacterial Isolates Sequence Results*

- D1 10-3 25M_1492R_012.seq.txt
- D1 10-3 25M_27F_079.seq.txt
- C 10-2 4M_1492R_014.seq.txt
- C 10-2 4M_27F_050.seq.txt
- B 10-2 4.5 M_1492R_004.seq.txt
- B 10-2 4.5 M_27F_071.seq.txt
- A 10-2 M_1492R_010.seq.txt
- A 10-2 M_27F_077.txt

APPENDIX D

➤ *BLAST Sequence(Forward -r and Reverse-r) results of the Unknown Bacterial Isolates A, B, C, and F.*

Job Title: A10_27F_077.ab1
RID: 526XEC56013
Program: BLASTN
Database: nt
Query ID: lcl|Query_104849
Description: A10_27F_077.ab1
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 1255

Filter Results:
Organism: only top 20 will appear
Percent Identity: 96.87 to []
E value: 0.00.0 to 0.0
Query Coverage: 100 to 95

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
Acinetobacter baumannii strain SZH13 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter bauma...	2017	2017	95%	0.0	96.87%	1287	GU384264.1
Acinetobacter sp. DSM30007 gene for 16S ribosomal RNA, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp.	2002	2002	96%	0.0	96.07%	1452	LC437022.1
Bacterium strain BS2086 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	bacterium	1993	1993	97%	0.0	95.50%	1438	MK825274.1
Acinetobacter sp. strain HSTU-ABk29 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp.	1991	1991	97%	0.0	95.43%	1436	MK695711.1

Af

Job Title: A10_1492R_010.ab1
RID: 527MJZMF01N
Program: BLASTN
Database: nt
Query ID: lcl|Query_298155
Description: A10_1492R_010.ab1
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 857

Filter Results:
Organism: only top 20 will appear
Percent Identity: [] to []
E value: [] to []
Query Coverage: [] to []

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
Acinetobacter baumannii strain HCC3 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter bauma...	433	433	31%	4e-116	94.16%	962	MW367578.1
Acinetobacter baumannii strain 29D2 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter bauma...	429	2577	31%	5e-115	94.76%	3836532	CP113069.1
Acinetobacter baumannii isolate GIMC5508:ABT-3Ts65 chromosome	Acinetobacter bauma...	429	2577	31%	5e-115	94.76%	3848390	CP120894.1

Ar

Job Title B10_27F_071.ab1
RID 527SSFH0013 Search expires on 05-03 22:32 pm Download All
Program BLASTN Citation
Database nt See details
Query ID lcl|Query_44161
Description B10_27F_071.ab1
Molecule type dna
Query Length 966
Other reports Distance tree of results MSA viewer

Filter Results
Organism only top 20 will appear exclude
 Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name
 + Add organism
Percent Identity to
E value to
Query Coverage to
 Filter Reset

Sequences producing significant alignments Download Select columns Show 100

select all 100 sequences selected GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results MSA Viewer

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain BUK_001 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	534	534	44%	1e-146	89.02%	1000	MN708958.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter sp. strain A18 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp.	534	534	42%	1e-146	89.88%	912	MH638274.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter sp. ZPP2 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp. ZPP2	534	534	42%	1e-146	89.88%	1204	KT763083.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain st10 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	532	532	43%	4e-146	89.71%	1460	MF102141.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain A1 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	532	532	42%	1e-146	89.71%	1020	OM760619.1

Bf

Job Title B10_1492R_004.ab1
RID 527WSA57016 Search expires on 05-03 22:35 pm Download All
Program BLASTN Citation
Database nt See details
Query ID lcl|Query_54705
Description B10_1492R_004.ab1
Molecule type dna
Query Length 931
Other reports Distance tree of results MSA viewer

Filter Results
Organism only top 20 will appear exclude
 Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name
 + Add organism
Percent Identity to
E value to
Query Coverage to
 Filter Reset

Sequences producing significant alignments Download Select columns Show 100

select all 100 sequences selected GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results MSA Viewer

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Uncultured bacterium clone P4D7-665 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	uncultured bacterium	719	719	44%	0.0	96.88%	1474	EF509893.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain JAB144 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	717	4305	44%	0.0	96.88%	3994773	CP121625.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain MAB17 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	717	4305	44%	0.0	96.88%	3962360	CP121595.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain RAB53 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	717	4305	44%	0.0	96.88%	3997089	CP121579.1

Br

NCBI Blast:F10_27F_075.ab1 x Acinetobacter baumannii - Wikip x +

blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi

Job Title F10_27F_075.ab1
RID 528D2G9K013 Search expires on 05-03 22:43 pm [Download All](#) v
Program BLASTN [Citation](#) v
Database nt [See details](#) v
Query ID lcl|Query_21125
Description F10_27F_075.ab1
Molecule type dna
Query Length 797
Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) ?

Filter Results

Organism only top 20 will appear exclude
 Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name
[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to **E value** to **Query Coverage** to
[Filter](#) [Reset](#)

Descriptions Graphic Summary Alignments Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download v Select columns v Show 100 ?

select all 100 sequences selected [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA Viewer](#)

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter sp. strain A18 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp.	708	708	51%	0.0	97.32%	912	MH638274.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter sp. ZPP2 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter sp. ZPP2	708	708	51%	0.0	97.32%	1204	KT763083.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain SM01 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	706	706	51%	0.0	96.88%	1127	MT444986.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain st10 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	706	706	51%	0.0	96.88%	1460	MF102141.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain A1 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	706	706	51%	0.0	96.88%	1039	OM760518.1

30°C Partly cloudy Search 10:44 pm 02/05/2023

NCBI Blast:D1-B10_1492R_012.ab1 x Acinetobacter baumannii - Wikip x +

blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi

Job Title D1-B10_1492R_012.ab1
RID 528MC8VV013 Search expires on 05-03 22:47 pm [Download All](#) v
Program BLASTN [Citation](#) v
Database nt [See details](#) v
Query ID lcl|Query_57631
Description D1-B10_1492R_012.ab1
Molecule type dna
Query Length 900
Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) ?

Filter Results

Organism only top 20 will appear exclude
 Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name
[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to **E value** to **Query Coverage** to
[Filter](#) [Reset](#)

Descriptions Graphic Summary Alignments Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download v Select columns v Show 100 ?

select all 100 sequences selected [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA Viewer](#)

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain JAB144 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	470	2821	32%	3e-127	94.48%	3994773	CP121625.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain MAB17 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	470	2821	32%	3e-127	94.48%	3962360	CP121595.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain RAB53 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	470	2821	32%	3e-127	94.48%	3997089	CP121579.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acinetobacter baumannii strain MAB16 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	470	2821	32%	3e-127	94.48%	4077512	CP121604.1

30°C Partly cloudy Search 10:48 pm 02/05/2023

Job Title: F10_1492R_008.ab1
RID: 529NSMRW016
Program: BLASTN
Database: nt
Query ID: lcl|Query_40957
Description: F10_1492R_008.ab1
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 794

Filter Results:
 Organism: exclude
 Percent Identity: to
 E value: to
 Query Coverage: to
 Filter Reset

Sequences producing significant alignments:

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
Acinetobacter baumannii strain VB1190 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	723	3256	56%	0.0	94.60%	3294487	CP040047.1
Acinetobacter baumannii strain M164-3 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	723	4292	56%	0.0	94.60%	3812291	CP058729.1
Acinetobacter baumannii strain SL12 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Acinetobacter baumannii	723	723	56%	0.0	94.60%	1376	KJ996152.1
Klebsiella pneumoniae strain KP59 chromosome	Klebsiella pneumoniae	723	5471	56%	0.0	94.60%	6064517	CP076322.1
Acinetobacter baumannii strain abA1 chromosome, complete genome	Acinetobacter baumannii	723	4311	56%	0.0	94.60%	4103762	CP060732.1

Job Title: C10_1492R_014.ab1
RID: 528SWWTG016
Program: BLASTN
Database: nt
Query ID: lcl|Query_14623
Description: C10_1492R_014.ab1
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 794

Filter Results:
 Organism: exclude
 Percent Identity: to
 E value: to
 Query Coverage: to
 Filter Reset

Sequences producing significant alignments:

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
Paenibacillus dendritiformis strain ClcZ203 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus de...	422	422	35%	7e-113	91.93%	1502	MN055964.1
Paenibacillus sp. strain 3179 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus sp.	422	422	35%	7e-113	91.93%	1413	MK616148.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis, partial 16S rRNA gene, strain Marseille-P568	Paenibacillus de...	422	422	35%	7e-113	91.93%	1514	LT732643.1
Paenibacillus sp. HK1 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus sp...	422	422	35%	7e-113	91.93%	1402	KT781678.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis strain RBTS3 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus de...	422	422	35%	7e-113	91.93%	1481	OQ824979.1

Cr

Job Title: C10_27F_050.ab1
RID: 528XYCR5013
Program: BLASTN
Database: nt
Query ID: lcl|Query_60699
Description: C10_27F_050.ab1
Molecule type: dna
Query Length: 1081

Filter Results:
 Organism: only top 20 will appear
 Percent Identity: [] to []
 E value: [] to []
 Query Coverage: [] to []

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
Paenibacillus sp. strain 3179 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus sp.	1083	1083	59%	0.0	95.97%	1413	MK616148.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis strain ClaCZ203 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus de...	1081	1081	59%	0.0	95.83%	1502	MN055964.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis J27TS7 DNA, complete genome	Paenibacillus de...	1081	8629	59%	0.0	95.83%	6547390	AP025344.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis J27TS7 gene for 16S rRNA, partial sequence	Paenibacillus de...	1081	1081	59%	0.0	95.83%	1506	LC588525.1
Paenibacillus dendritiformis strain RRLKE4 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	Paenibacillus de...	1081	1081	59%	0.0	95.83%	1484	HQ625389.1

APPENDIX E

➤ *Catalase Test Results: Smears of the Coded Bacterial Isolates on Slides with Droplets of 3% Hydrogen Peroxide.*

APPENDIX F

➤ *Oxidase Test Results: Oxidase Test Discs Applied with Smears of the Coded Bacterial Isolates.*

